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RESEARCH ARTICLE

EFFECT OF ORGANIC SEED PRIMING ON YIELD AND YIELD ATTRIBUTING TRAITS OF CHICKPEA (*Cicer arietinum* L.) IN DROUGHT PRONE AREA

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ABSTRACT

The goals of this study are to evaluate the suitable variety and priming method and find out the interaction effect of seed priming and variety for maximization of chickpea yield and yield attributes at drought-prone region. The Agronomy Research Plot of Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur, Bangladesh led this experiment during November 2021 to April 2022 following randomized complete block design with three replications. The experiment had two factors: (A) two chickpea varieties, V1= BARI Chola-10 and V2= BARI Chola-11, and (B) five priming treatments, P1= Control (No priming), P2= Hydropriming, P3= *Alovera* leaf extract, P4= *Azadirachta indica* leaf extract, and P5= *Moringa olifera* leaf extract. It was manifested that BARI Chola-10 (V1) exhibited the superior performance in the yield and yield attributing traits subjected to no. of pods plant⁻¹ (5.62), no. of seeds plant⁻¹ (2.18), 1000 seeds weight (207.8 g), grain (1.76 t ha⁻¹), stover (2.71 t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (4.48 t ha⁻¹). In varied priming treatments, P5 (*Moringa olifera* leaf extract) produced the most grain yield (2.07 t ha⁻¹), whereas control (P1) produced the least (1.35 t ha⁻¹). The maximal stover yield was 2.72 t ha⁻¹ with *Moringa olifera* leaf extract and the lowest was 2.40 t ha⁻¹ without priming. The treatment combination V1P5 performed best in extent of grain (2.13 t ha⁻¹) and stover yield (2.83 t ha⁻¹) whereas the minimum seed yield (1.30 t ha⁻¹) and stover yield (2.26 t ha⁻¹) were recorded from V2P1 treatment combination. BARI Chola-10 (V1) primed with *Moringa olifera* leaf extract (P5) improved chickpea yield in the study region.

KEYWORDS

Cicer arietinum, Drought-prone, Organic seed priming, Yield, *Moringa olifera*

1. INTRODUCTION

In a scenario of steady economic development, agricultural demand is predicted to rise by 50% from 2013 to 2050 as the global population approaches 10 billion (FAO, 2017). Food and nutritional security for a growing population in the face of global climate change requires a second green revolution. Due to their low production cost and symbiotic nitrogen fixing, grain legumes are the best choice. Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) under the family of legumes, Fabaceae is a staple crop worldwide, notably in Afro-Asia.

It is an excellent storehouse of carbohydrate and protein, and its protein quality is superior than other pulses. Chickpeas contains calcium, zinc, magnesium, phosphate, manganese, iron, and vitamin K (Wood and Grusak, 2007). Chickpeas provide all necessary amino acids except sulphur-containing ones, which can be supplemented with grains.

Chickpea, the third most significant pulse crop, is farmed on 12 million hectares of land from temperate to subtropical climates, with 72% of global output from South Asia (Foyer et al., 2016). Chickpea production in Bangladesh is 4942 metric tonnes on 4634.41 hectares (BBS, 2021).

Chickpea seeds are categorised by size, shape, and colour. Kabuli and Desi, two different gene pools, are the primary chickpea cultivars worldwide.

Where Northern India grows white-seeded 'Kabuli chickpea' while Southern India grows brown-seeded 'Desi'. Desi kinds have thick, brown seed coats, whereas kabuli types have thin, cream-colored coats (Rizvi et al., 2014).

From anthesis to maturity, water stress impacts several plant morphological and physiological processes, reducing agricultural yield and productivity. Chickpea growth and productivity are limited by water stress worldwide (Manjunath and Dhanoji, 2010). However, chickpea in drought stress during pre-anthesis reduced chlorophyll, seed storage protein, plant height, and pods and increased total phenolic content and antioxidants such proline, SOD, APX, and MDA.

Seed priming, a promising method, improves crop vigour, nutritional value, grain, and biological yield by overcoming poor germination, dormancy, and inconsistent crop stand under normal and stressed conditions (Jafar et al., 2012). CaCl₂, KNO₃, NaCl, KH₂PO₄ and KCl are popular priming agents. These inorganic priming techniques disrupt seed dormancy, promote uniform germination, rapid development, and reduce drought stress on emergence. Hydro priming, osmo priming, matrix priming, and drum-priming are currently available priming methods. Thus, developing simple, practicable, and viable technology to boost seedling vigour and establishment under different climatic circumstances is crucial. Seed priming is a straightforward, low-cost, low-risk chickpea

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stand establishing method suitable for all farmers, regardless of socioeconomic position. Seed priming can increase crop emergence, although soil moisture regime is the most essential soil physical feature. The mechanism and duration of priming determine its effect. Over-primed seeds perish in excess soil moisture, but drying insufficient soil moisture can also produce poor stand establishment (Saha et al., 2006). It improves germination, plant height, leaf number, leaf area, and grain number, tiller number, grain weight, and crop production. This is because cow pee includes growth regulators, minerals, and trace elements (Joseph and Nair, 1989; Chawla, 1986). This method has been used in several crops, including chickpea, to increase germination speed, mean germination time, and seedling vigour, especially in drought and stress. In the synthetic world, chemical seed priming affects the seed and soil environment. Priming seeds with organic is safe, practical, eco-friendly, cheap, and easy to perform on farm. Organic seed priming resists heat and drought in semi-arid tropical regions.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1 Site of the experiment

The investigation was conducted between November 2021 to April 2022 at the Agronomy Research Field of Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University (HSTU), Dinajpur-5200. The experimental area is situated at 25° 38' N latitude, 88° 41' E longitude, and 37 m above the sea level. The experimental location was a medium-high land under the Agro-ecological Zone-1 (AEZ-1), also known as the Old Himalayan Piedmont Plain (UNDP and FAO, 1998). Soil pH of the site ranges from 5.8 to 6.0 and organic matter was 1.48%. The property is well-drained and above flood level. The experimental area was included under the subtropical climate.

2.2 Planting Materials and Experimental Design

The BARI Chola-10 and BARI Chola-11 varieties were utilized to conduct the present investigation. The seedlings were gathered from Agronomy Division of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh. The two factors study was constructed in randomized complete block design with three replications. Each block has 10 plots with 5 random treatment combinations. The plot measured 10 m². The distance between blocks and plots was 1 m. Two chickpea genotypes: V₁ = BARI Chola-10 and V₂ = BARI Chola-11 and five seed priming agents: P₁ = Normal seed (Control), P₂ = Hydro priming (Distilled Water), P₃ = *Alovera* leaf extract, P₄ = *Azadirachta indica* leaf extract and P₅ = *Moringa olifera* leaf extract were used in this study.

2.3 Land Preparation

The experimental field was prepared with the help of a power tiller and exposed to sun for five to six days before ploughing again. Thus, the ground was ploughed, cross-ploughed, and deep-ploughed to acquire the condition of good tilth. After each ploughing, laddering broke the soil clods into little pieces. All weeds and stubbles were removed from the experimental field. The plots were spaded one day before planting and all fertilisers were fully introduced according to the recommendation doses of (BARI (2014).

2.4 Fertilizer Application

Urea, Triple super phosphate (TSP), Muriate of potash (MOP), and Boric acid were used as a source of nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium and boron at the rate of 45, 85, 35 and 11 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. All the fertilizers were collected from the farm of HSTU. During the period of land preparation TSP, MOP and half of Urea used as basal application, rest of urea provided in two splits.

2.5 Sowing of Seeds

The seeds were planted on November 19, 2021 following the distance between rows and plants was 30 cm and 10 cm, respectively. The seeds were planted approximately 1 to 2 cm below the soil's surface. 90% of seeds germinated on the fifth day following sowing.

2.6 Intercultural Operations

2.6.1 Thinning and Weeding

Seedling emerged ten days after seeding. Overcrowded seedlings were trimmed twice. First-thinning was done fifteen days after seeding to

eliminate sick and displaced seedlings. The second thinning occurred ten days following the first. Keeping the plots weed-free for ensuring optimum growth and development of the seedlings. Weeding was done at 30 days after sowing (DAS) and thereafter as needed in experimental plots.

2.6.2 Irrigation and Drainage

Required amount of watering was done to maintain till soil saturation at 30 days after sowing (DAS). Heavy showers discharged to avoid stagnant situation.

2.6.3 Harvesting, Threshing and Cleaning

The crop was hand collected from each plot on 27 April 2022 after 80% of the pods matured. The harvested produce from each plot was packed, labelled, and carried to the threshing floor. Chickpea seed was harvested, threshed, and cleaned carefully.

2.7 Data Collection Procedure

The data of the different parameters of chickpea were collected from randomly selected five plant samples which were collected from each plot. The data were recorded from 30 days after sowing (DAS) and continued until the end of recording of yield contributing characters of the characters of the crop after harvest. The following yield attributing traits (number of pods plant⁻¹, number of Seeds pod⁻¹ and 1000 seeds weight) and yield traits (grain yield, stover yield, biological yield and harvest index) were recorded.

2.7.1 Number of Pods and Seeds Plant⁻¹

Total pods of five plants from each plot were counted and the mean was given on the basis of per plant. Total seeds of five plants were collected from each plot and estimated the mean number based on per pod.

2.7.2 Weight of 1000 Seeds (g)

One thousand cleaned and dried seeds were randomly counted from each sample and weighed using a digital electric balance to calculate the mean weight in grammes.

2.7.3 Grain Yield (t ha⁻¹)

All the plants of the whole plot were collected together to measure the grain yield. Later the grains were threshed from the plants and weighed after cleaning and drying in the sun. The grain yield in kg plot⁻¹ was adjusted to 12% moisture content and then it was converted to t ha⁻¹.

2.7.4 Stover Yield (t ha⁻¹)

Harvested plants of each plot were dried in the sun until the stover achieved a constant weight. The stover was then weighted, and stover yield plot⁻¹ was calculated. The yield of stover was converted from kg plot⁻¹ to t ha⁻¹.

2.7.5 Biological yield (t ha⁻¹)

Grain yield and stover yield together were regarded as biological yield. The biological yield was calculated with the following formula:

$$\text{Biological yield} = \text{Grain yield} + \text{Stover yield}$$

2.7.6 Harvest index (%)

The ratio of grain yield to biological yield was used to determine the harvest index, which was then expressed as a per cent. It was determined via the formula below:

$$\text{Harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Grain yield}}{\text{Biological yield}} \times 100$$

2.8 Statistical Analysis

On Excel documents, data collected from various parameters were compiled and arranged in an orderly fashion. A statistical programme, Statistix-10, used to conduct the accurate statistical analysis from the collected data. The Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was followed to compare the treatment means (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effect of Varieties on Yield and Yield Attributing Traits

In case of number of pods plant⁻¹ and seeds plant⁻¹, highly significant variation was observed between the two varieties (Table 1). BARI Chola-10 (V1) had the most pods plant⁻¹ (5.62), followed by BARI Chola-11 (V2). The maximal number of pods plant⁻¹ (5.62) and seeds plant⁻¹ (2.18) was observed from BARI Chola-10 (V1) and the minimal number of pods plant⁻¹ (4.73) and seeds plant⁻¹ (1.87) was noted from BARI Chola-11 (V2). The highest quantity of thousand seeds weight was 207.8 g from V1 (BARI

Chola-10), while the minimum was 190.5 g from V2. Table 1 showed that no significant difference in seed yield between BARI Chola-10 and BARI Chola-11. Grain yield (1.76 t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (4.48 t ha⁻¹) was greater from V1 (BARI Chola-10) and lower extent of grain and biological yield (1.65, 4.114 t ha⁻¹, respectively) from V2 (BARI Chola-11). Chickpea stover output and harvest index varied greatly depending to varieties (Table 1). BARI Chola-11 gave the peak quantity of stover yield (2.71 t ha⁻¹) followed by BARI Chola-10 (2.48 t ha⁻¹). It was noticed that highest per cent of harvest index (39.82) was achieved from V2 (BARI Chola-11), whereas it was the lowest (39.18) from V1 (BARI Chola-10).

Table 1: Effect of varieties and priming on number of pods plant⁻¹, number of seeds pod⁻¹, 1000 seeds weight (g), grain yield (t ha⁻¹), stover yield (t ha⁻¹), biological yield (t ha⁻¹), harvest index (%) of chickpea

Treatment	No. of pods plant ⁻¹	No. of seeds pod ⁻¹	1000 seeds weight (g)	Grain Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Stover yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biological yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
Variety							
V1	5.62a	2.18a	207.8a	1.76a	2.71a	4.48a	39.18a
V2	4.73b	1.87b	190.5b	1.65b	2.48b	4.14b	39.82a
LSD	0.48	0.17	0.75	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.97
CV	12.18	11.29	4.95	5.63	5.10	5.05	3.22
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	*
Priming							
P1	4.10c	1.65c	172.4c	1.35d	2.40c	3.75d	36.06c
P2	4.78bc	1.89bc	182.7c	1.53c	2.55b	4.09c	37.54c
P3	5.48b	2.11b	211.5b	1.82b	2.63ab	4.45b	41.03b
P4	4.91b	2b	201.3b	1.76b	2.68a	4.46b	39.71b
P5	6.61a	2.49a	228.0a	2.07a	2.72a	4.80a	43.17a
LSD	0.48	0.17	0.75	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.97
CV	12.18	11.29	4.95	5.63	5.10	5.05	3.22
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Here, * indicates 5% level of probability and ** indicates 1% level of probability

3.2 Effect Of Priming On Yield And Yield Attributing Traits

Different yield and yield contributing traits of chickpea were diverse due to the impact of different priming (Table 1). P5 (*Moringa olifera* leaf extract) had the maximum number of pods plant⁻¹ (6.61) and seeds plant⁻¹ (2.49) statistically equivalent to P3 (*Alovera* leaf extract), whereas P1 had the lowest number of pods plant⁻¹ (4.10) and seeds plant⁻¹ (1.65) when no treatment was used. P5 (228 g) yielded the greatest chickpea thousand seed weight, whereas P1 (control) produced the lowest (172.4 g). The top quantity of grain (2.07 t ha⁻¹), stover (2.72 t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (4.80 t ha⁻¹) were recorded from P5, while it was the minimum (1.35, 2.40 and 3.75 t ha⁻¹, respectively) in control (P1). The highest content of harvest index (43.17 %) was estimated from P5 followed by P3 (41.03 %) and P4 (39.71 %).

3.3 Interaction Effect of Variety and Priming on Yield and Yield Attributing Traits

Variety and priming significantly affected harvest pods plant⁻¹ (Table 2). The V1P5 (BARI Chola-10 and *Moringa olifera* leaf extract) had the most pods plant⁻¹ (7.33) and the least (3.83), which was statistically different from other combinations. Chickpea varieties and priming treatments interacted to cause significant variance on seeds pod⁻¹ (Table 2). V1P5 (BARI Chola-10 and *Moringa olifera* leaf extract) had the highest seeds

pod⁻¹ (2.83) and V2P1 (BARI Chola-11 and control, no priming) had the lowest (1.48). Interaction impact between chickpea types and priming treatments affected 1000 seed weight (Table 2). V2P1 (BARI Chola-11 and control) had the lowest 1000 seed weight (165.6g) and V1P5 (BARI Chola-10 and *Moringa olifera* leaf extract) the highest (237.8 g). A strong interaction effect between chickpea varieties and priming treatments affected grain yield (Table 2). The combination V1P5 (BARI Chola-10 and *Moringa olifera* leaf extract) yielded the most seeds (2.13 t ha⁻¹) followed by V2P5 (2.13 t ha⁻¹) and V1P3 (1.88 t ha⁻¹). Recorded maximum stover yield (t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (t ha⁻¹) were got at V1P5 (2.83 and 4.96, respectively). Chickpea biological yield varied significantly with variety and priming (Table 2). Combination was observed getting maximal biological yield (t ha⁻¹) at V1P5 (4.96) which was followed by V1P3 (4.64), V2P5 (4.63), V1P4 (4.58). The lowest biological yield (3.56 t ha⁻¹) was from V2P1 (BARI Chola-11 and Control, no priming), which was statistically different. V2P5 (BARI Chola-10 and *Moringa olifera* leaf extract) recorded the highest harvest index (43.53), while V1P1 was the lowest (35.62). Interaction effect of chickpea varieties and different priming treatments showed statistically significant variation in terms of harvest index (Table 2). The maximum harvest index (43.53 %) was recorded from V₂P₅ (BARI Chola-10 and *Moringa olifera* leaf extract) which was statistically similar with other combinations whereas the minimum harvest index (35.62 %) was observed from V₁P₁ (BARI Chola-10 and Control i.e. no priming) combination which was statistically similar with V₂P₁.

Table 2: Interaction effect of varieties and priming on number of pods plant⁻¹, number of seeds pod⁻¹, 1000 seeds weight (g), grain yield (t ha⁻¹), stover yield (t ha⁻¹), biological yield (t ha⁻¹), harvest index (%) of chickpea

Treatment		No. of pods plant ⁻¹	No. of seeds pod ⁻¹	1000 seeds weight (g)	Grain Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Stover Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biological Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest Index (%)
V1	P1	4.36de	1.83bcd	179.3ef	1.40fg	2.53	3.93d	35.62d
	P2	4.93bcd	2.00bc	189.5de	1.60de	2.67	4.28c	37.47cd
	P3	6.00b	2.20b	221.5ab	1.88bc	2.76	4.64b	40.51b
	P4	5.50bc	2.08bc	211.1bc	1.81c	2.77	4.58b	39.51bc
	P5	7.33a	2.83a	237.8a	2.13a	2.83	4.96a	42.80a
V2	P1	3.83e	1.48d	165.6f	1.30g	2.26	3.56e	36.50d
	P2	4.63cde	1.78cd	175.9ef	1.46ef	2.43	3.90d	37.61cd
	P3	4.96bcd	2.02bc	201.5cd	1.77c	2.49	4.27c	41.56ab
	P4	4.33de	1.92bc	191.5de	1.72cd	2.60	4.32c	39.91b
	P5	5.90b	2.16bc	218.2bc	2.02ab	2.61	4.63b	43.53a
LSD		0.48	0.17	0.75	0.07	0.06	0.10	0.97
CV (%)		12.18	11.29	4.95	5.63	5.11	5.05	3.22
LS		*	*	*	*	ns	*	*

Here, *indicates 5% level of probability and ** indicates 1% level of probability

4. DISCUSSION

Water-based seed priming triggers the metabolic activation process during the germination. Seed health also depends on priming and plants germinated through healthy and vigorous seeds have full growth and development and productivity also increases. Organic sources of seed priming act as an antifungal, antimicrobial, anti-oxidants in seed and influences the nutrients status and immunity power and plays role as a growth promoter. Priming strategies may improve uniform germination and develops the behavior of the obtained seedlings in terms of plant growth and stress resistance (Zheng et al., 2015). Over priming may cause oxygen deficiency and the build-up of inhibitors (Murray, 1989). Priming significantly decreased thermal time requirements (Hardegrete et al., 2002). However, the benefit of seed priming depends on many seed and field factors including the selection of preplant seed treatments. Pulses' pod number is heavily affected by nutrition. Harvest variations greatly affected plant⁻¹'s pod count. Genetical constituents, environment, and management practices, nutrient availability may affect variety variation. The found no significant changes in plant pod count amongst cultivars (Mirzakhani et al., 2013). As a reported substantial heterogeneity in chickpea pods plant⁻¹, whereas found the opposite (Bhuiyan et al., 2009). The pod⁻¹ seed count is a key yield factor (Khatun et al., 2010). Grain yield increases with pod⁻¹ seed count. Thus, more photosynthate mobilisation to individual grains compensated for fewer seeds per plant, allowing BARI Chola-10 to produce larger seeds. Genotypes with longer pod development periods would have higher seed growth, which would maintain yield. Input supply, culture method, and growing season environment affected seed pod⁻¹ number for different types. Seed weight affects agricultural productivity (Singh and Sekhon, 2006). To recorded thousands of seeds weighing 110-120g in BARI Chola-5, 140-150g in BARI Chola-6, and 250-260g in BARI Chola-8 (Khatun et al., 2010; Bhuiyan et al., 2009). The final manifestation of plant physiological and metabolic activity is grain yield per acre. The cumulative impact of all variables that improve growth increases grain production per plant and per hectare. Variety plays a vital part in achieving high chickpea output, and yield may vary owing to genetics, climate, and management. The found considerable grain yield differences in chickpea genotypes (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2007). Increased straw output is linked to plant vegetative growth and reproduction. stated that stover yield of chickpea were significantly influenced by sowing time (Husnain et al., 2015). Due to chickpea variety, discovered considerable stover yield fluctuation (Khatun et al., 2010; Bhuiyan et al., 2009). Sowing time differed a significantly in producing biological yield (Husnain et al., 2015). Sowing on December produced the highest biological yields (6.70 t ha⁻¹) of chickpea (Prasad et al., 2012). The harvest index is grain/straw yield. Variety treatments did not affect harvest index.

5. CONCLUSION

The present experiment suggests that various priming had a beneficial effect on the overall physiology, growth, and yield of chickpea. In terms of statistical significance, the highest yield was achieved with treatment

P5=*Moringa olifera* leaf extract. Maximum results were seen across the board for growth and yield metrics for BARI Chola-10 (V1). Chickpeas benefit greatly from a combination of P5=*Moringa olifera* leaf extract and the BARI Chola-10 (V1) variety. The present results may be validated, however, if this feature were to be repeated in other Agro ecological zones of Bangladesh.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

MSIS and MSH proposed the conception, designed the project and methodology; MSY collected materials for this experiment, performed field work and collected data; MMH and NCH conducted data analysis and wrote and revised the manuscript. All authors read and approve the manuscript.

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AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

The data and materials of this experiment are presented in the manuscript.

DECLARATIONS

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Not applicable

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable

COMPETING INTERESTS

The author declare they have no competing interests.

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